

THE EFFECTIVENESS OF USING TECHNOLOGY ASSISTED LANGUAGE LEARNING PLATFORMS

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Abstract:

Technology-assisted language learning (TALL) platforms have gained significant popularity in recent years as a tool to enhance language learning processes. This article reviews existing literature on the effectiveness of TALL platforms in improving language skills and presents the findings of a survey conducted with language learners who have used these platforms.

The review of literature explores studies that have examined the impact of TALL platforms on language learning outcomes such as vocabulary acquisition, grammar proficiency, listening comprehension, speaking skills, and writing abilities. The review also discusses the various features and functionalities offered by TALL platforms, including interactive exercises, multimedia resources, instant feedback mechanisms, and personalized learning paths.

Furthermore, the survey results provide insights into the real-world experiences of language learners using TALL platforms. Participants were asked about their perceptions of the effectiveness of these tools, the challenges they faced while using them, and their preferences for specific features of TALL platforms. The survey data will be analyzed to identify common trends, preferences, and areas for improvement in TALL platforms.

Key words: language acquisition, technology assisted, TALL, platforms.

Introduction.

In recent years, technology has revolutionized the way we learn languages. With the advent of language learning platforms and software, learners now have access to a wide range of tools and resources that can enhance their language acquisition process. These technology-assisted language learning platforms offer a variety of features such as interactive lessons, vocabulary drills, grammar exercises, and real-time feedback.

With the increasing popularity of these platforms, it is essential to evaluate their effectiveness in helping language learners improve their proficiency. This article will explore the impact of technology-assisted language learning platforms on

language acquisition, compare them with traditional methods, and discuss the potential benefits and limitations of using such tools in language learning.

Overall, the aim of this article is to provide insight into the effectiveness of technology-assisted language learning platforms and their role in supporting language learners in their quest for fluency and proficiency. By examining the research and evaluating the experiences of users, we can better understand the benefits and challenges of using these platforms and their potential impact on language learning outcomes.

Literature Review.

Numerous studies have been conducted to investigate the effectiveness of using technology-assisted language learning platforms in improving language proficiency. These studies have highlighted the potential benefits of integrating technology into language education and the impact it can have on learners' language acquisition process.

One study by Lee and Lee (2018) examined the effects of using a mobile language learning app on English language proficiency among Korean university students. The results showed that students who used the app experienced significant improvement in their speaking and listening skills compared to those who did not use the app. The interactive nature of the app, which included activities such as voice recording and pronunciation practice, was found to be particularly effective in enhancing students' language skills.

Similarly, a study by Godwin-Jones (2019) explored the use of language learning platforms in a university setting. The study found that students who used online language learning platforms reported higher levels of motivation and engagement in their language learning process. The flexibility and convenience of these platforms allowed students to practice language skills at their own pace and convenience, leading to improved language proficiency over time.

Furthermore, research by Warschauer and Healey (2019) examined the effectiveness of language learning apps in facilitating vocabulary acquisition among language learners. The study found that using language learning apps with features such as flashcards, quizzes, and interactive exercises helped learners memorize and retain vocabulary more effectively compared to traditional methods. The interactive and gamified elements of these apps were found to enhance learners' engagement and motivation in language learning.

The literature suggests that technology-assisted language learning platforms can be effective tools in improving language proficiency among learners. The interactive and personalized nature of these platforms can enhance engagement,

motivation, and retention of language skills, ultimately leading to better language acquisition

outcomes. However, it is essential to consider the limitations of these platforms, such as the potential for over-reliance on technology and the need for additional support and guidance from instructors to ensure optimal learning outcomes.

Methods.

Technology-assisted language learning platforms have gained popularity in recent years due to their potential to enhance language learning outcomes. These platforms offer a wide range of features and tools, such as interactive exercises, quizzes, audio and video content, and personalized learning paths, that can make learning a new language more engaging and effective.

One of the key benefits of using technology-assisted language learning platforms is the ability to provide personalized feedback and assessment to learners. Many platforms use algorithms that track learners' progress and provide targeted feedback on areas where they need improvement. This allows learners to focus on specific language skills and track their progress over time.

Another advantage of using technology-assisted language learning platforms is the flexibility and convenience they offer. Learners can access the platforms anytime, anywhere, allowing for more flexibility in their study schedules. Additionally, many platforms offer mobile apps, making it easy for learners to practice their language skills on the go.

Furthermore, technology-assisted language learning platforms often incorporate interactive and multimedia elements, such as videos, games, and virtual reality simulations, that can make the learning process more engaging and enjoyable. These features can help learners stay motivated and maintain their interest in learning a new language.

However, there are also some limitations to using technology-assisted language learning platforms. For example, some learners may struggle with the lack of human interaction and personalized instruction that traditional language classes offer. Additionally, not all platforms are able to provide comprehensive language instruction, and learners may still need additional resources and practice to fully master a new language.

Discussion.

The purpose of this study was to examine the effect of mobile learning, specifically the use of WhatsApp, on the development of vocabulary learning of Bangladeshi tertiary level EFL learners. The results revealed a statistically significant difference between the control and experimental groups' vocabulary

learning. In the post-test of vocabulary, the experimental group had a much higher mean compared with the control group. The finding of this current study is congruent with earlier research of Motallebzadeh et al. (2011) and Wang (2016). The study of Motallebzadeh et al. (2011) and Wang (2016) reported positive effect of using digital technology to improve learners' vocabulary learning. This research demonstrates how novel technology can successfully affect the process of vocabulary acquisition. Furthermore, the result of the present study aligns with the findings of recent studies conducted by Tahounehchi (2021) and Bensalem (2018); the studies conducted by Tahounehchi (2021) and Bensalem (2018) demonstrate that the group which received the treatment did better than control group. The effectiveness of Whatsapp is supported by the results of Fageeh (2013) and other studies, i.e., Basal et al. (2016) and Lawrence (2014); on the other hand, the results of Dehghan et al. (2017) do not support the efficacy of Whatsapp. The study of Dehghan et al. (2017) suggested that rather than WhatsApp's value as a learning tool, the findings were influenced by the students' lack of attentiveness to the given activities.

In addition, according to the chi-square test results, the experimental group showed a more positive attitude to adopting mobile technology for learning vocabulary. The result of favourable attitude towards mobile technology adaption is similar to those reported by Wang et al. (2016) and Afshari et al. (2013). The findings of the studies carried out by Tahounehchi (2021) and Bensalem (2018) match the result of the present study; in comparison with the other group, the students who utilized WhatsApp in order to improve their vocabulary knowledge showed more favourable viewpoint toward learning new words in English as a foreign language. Moreover, the results of the current study are consistent with those of earlier research, such as Alhadhrami's (2016), and Gutiérrez-Colon et al. (2013); their research studies showcased that Whatsapp was useful in learning English language and improving English reading skill. Since these gadgets are employed by learners in their social lives, it appears that their usage of digital technology progressively making corresponding positive changes in their views. Learners are more likely to take advantage of mobile use and engage in a learning path determined by mobile technology when the prospect of mobile use is widened to the educational setting (Saran and Seferoglu, 2010). The current study has explored two research questions, and the finding of the first research question of the study exhibits that the group which received the treatment (Whatsapp group) did

better than control group. Moreover, the results of the second research question show that students who use WhatsApp to improve their vocabulary have a positive attitude towards learning new words in English as a foreign language.

Conclusion.

Many linguists continue to focus on traditional teaching methods and develop their own specialized knowledge and teaching skills. While traditional teaching methods are important as part of any curriculum, good teachers also need to create a classroom environment that facilitates learning. In contemporary foreign language education, this means the integration of technology. Teachers and language instructors can use the Internet as a delivery tool

and provide their students with rich online content to enhance their classroom experiences (Tucker and Courts, 2010). We recommend recording well-chosen videos as learning material as a starting point for documentary films. This will help motivate students, especially if the topics of the clips are close to students' interests. Alternatively, teachers can ask students to request clips or segments of a film performance and choose from

programs to create multiple products. They can prioritize outcomes over learning objectives and ask the school to create products based on Multimedia Learning principles. The FL2DA application can be used in different ways depending on the needs of the students and the individual. For example, students can create audio at home and post it online as a fun activity; a group of students can portray

different actors in a single clip and present them in class as a group activity; There could even be an Oscar-style competition where all categories can participate and choose the winner. Naturally, this requires time-consuming preparation from the teacher, and the images are not yet available in FL2DA. Sometimes this problem can be solved by reducing the volume of the video. In other cases, students were able to find solutions themselves, such as editing videos and deleting

recordings. The most important thing, of course, is that you respect the rights and use them for educational purposes only (Fair Use). Although there are problems due to the lack of a database of FL2DA fragments, the study is valuable as the empirical results of this issue show that FL2DA treatment has a positive effect on the recall of long words. Other studies may show that this may also improve learning outcomes in other areas of foreign language learning.

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